

Lived Experiences of Transitioning from a Private Instructor to a TESDA Instructor

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Abstract. This study aimed to seek and gain deeper understanding of how these individuals navigate their circumstances, the difficulties they encounter, and the strategies they employ to manage stress and adapt to their situations. The participants of the study are the former private instructors who are now currently employed as TESDA instructors. A purposive sampling technique is used to select 3-5 participants, ensuring that they have firsthand experience of the phenomenon being studied. The data from this research were examined through thematic analysis with the help of methodological triangulation to guarantee the reliability of the results. The data reveal that transitioning from private to TESDA instruction entails a multifaceted adjustment involving bureaucratic navigation, constrained autonomy, and evolving professional identity, significantly impacting instructors' teaching approaches and personal fulfillment. Despite the challenges encountered, former private instructors ultimately find renewed purpose and a sense of national contribution in their roles as TESDA educators, highlighting the resilience and adaptability required in such vocational transitions. The study's implications highlight the need for structured support systems, continuous professional development, and flexible policies to help former private instructors effectively transition into TESDA's competency-based and regulated teaching environment.

KEY WORDS

1. Experiences 2. transitioning 3. challenges

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1. Introduction

Transitioning from a private educational institution to a public or government-led agency like the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) is not merely a shift in employment—it is a complex personal and professional journey. Speaking from my own experience, I have come to realize that this transition presents significant challenges that go beyond adjusting to a new workplace. It involves confronting differences in organizational culture, teaching approaches, institutional expectations, and administrative systems. In private institutions, instructors often operate within a more structured and resource-supported environment. On the other hand, TESDA, as a government training institution, demands a broader understanding of national development goals, compliance with technical standards, and deeper engagement with community-based training. The shift, therefore, is not only technical in nature but also emotional and psychological. I have personally struggled to cope with these changes—feeling the weight of bureaucracy, adapting to new teaching method-

ologies, and finding my place in a system that operates quite differently from what I was used to. Across the globe, the importance of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) has gained increasing recognition as a strategic response to unemployment, skills mismatch, and economic development (UNESCO-UNECOV,2020) .TVET institutions serve as a bridge between education and the labor market, equipping learners with industry-relevant competencies. As the demand for skilled professionals continues to rise, many countries have strengthened their public TVET systems, which has, in turn, led to the absorption of experienced educators from the private sector into public institutions. Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) plays a vital role in addressing unemployment, reducing the gap between skills and job requirements, and promoting economic growth. These institutions provide practical and industry-based training that prepares individuals to meet the demands of the labor market. As more countries recognize the value of a skilled workforce, there has been a noticeable shift toward strengthening public TVET systems. This shift has opened opportunities for experienced professionals from the private sector to transition into public teaching roles, where they can share their expertise and contribute to workforce development. In the Philippines, the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) stands at the forefront of vocational education. It is mandated to manage and supervise the country's TVET system and to ensure its alignment with labor market needs (TESDA, 2022). Over the years, TESDA has seen an increase in the number of instructors transitioning from private training centers and institutions to government-run training centers. These transitions are influenced by factors such as job security, opportunities for professional development, and a desire to contribute to nation-building through public service (Manasan, 2020). However, this professional shift often entails significant adjustments. Private instructors, who are accustomed to flexible curricula and teaching autonomy, are required to conform to TESDA's national competency-based training regulations, assessment procedures, and institutional policies. The transition also involves adapting to the culture and expectations of a government-regulated institution which may affect the instructors' teaching styles, workload management, and professional identity. Locally, in Davao City, the research written by Kris Albert A. Monghit, 2025 examines the experiences of teachers in Davao City who have moved from private teaching roles to positions with the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA). In light of the city's increasing focus on technical-vocational education as a crucial factor for economic growth and workforce preparedness, grasping this professional transition is essential. The study investigates how local educators adjust to the teaching, administrative, and cultural changes that accompany the transition, providing insights into their motivations, difficulties, and personal development. As TESDA remains vital in developing skilled labor in Davao City and its surroundings, the insights of these instructors offer valuable viewpoints on the changing dynamics of vocational education in the area. TESDA-accredited Wangan National Agricultural School (WNAS) located in Calinan plays a vital role in providing TVET programs with a focus on agriculture, animal production, and other relevant technical skills. WNAS has welcomed instructors from private training institutions who bring diverse instructional practices, but who also face the need to adjust to government-mandated systems and resource limitations typical in public institutions (TESDA Davao Region, 2022). Investigating the lived experiences of these instructors offers valuable insights into the personal and professional transformations they undergo, as well as the institutional challenges and opportunities

they encounter during this transition.

1.1. Statement of the Problem—This study aims to explore the lived experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of individuals within a specific context. It seeks to gain a deeper understanding of how these individuals navigate their circumstances, the difficulties they encounter, and the strategies they employ to manage stress and adapt to their situations.

1. What are the lived experiences of the participants in relation to their current situation or environment?
2. What specific challenges or difficulties do they encounter in their personal, social, academic, or professional lives?
3. What coping mechanisms or strategies do they use to deal with these challenges?

2. Methodology

The choice of research design in this study is based on my personal insights and reflections as a researcher seeking to deeply understand the human experience behind professional transitions. While grounded in my own perspective, this explanation also draws upon established scholarly foundations to ensure clarity and rigor.

2.1. Research Design—This study employs a descriptive phenomenological research design, which is appropriate for exploring and describing the lived experiences of individuals who have transitioned from being private instructors to becoming TESDA instructors. Phenomenology, as described by Husserl (1970), aims to understand how individuals perceive and make sense of their experiences. This design is particularly suited to uncover the essence of the participants' experiences, focusing on their thoughts, feelings, challenges, and coping mechanisms during the transition process.

2.2. Research Respondents—The participants of this study are the former private instructors who are now currently employed as TESDA instructors. A purposive sampling technique is used to select 3-5 participants, ensuring

that they have firsthand experience of the phenomenon being studied. Inclusion criteria will include: (1) having taught in a private institution for at least one year, and (2) currently serving as a TESDA-accredited instructor for at least six months. This targeted sampling allows for in-depth exploration of their transition experiences in a meaningful and contextually grounded manner.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study employed a semi-structured interview guide as the primary research instrument. The interview guide was designed to elicit rich, detailed descriptions of the participants' lived experiences during their transition from private instruction to TESDA instruction. The guide included open-ended questions aligned with the central research questions and allowed for follow-up probing to explore deeper meanings.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The data from this research were examined through methodological triangulation to guarantee the reliability and validity of the results. Since the study examined the experiences of ex-private instructors moving to TESDA instructors, a descriptive phenomenological approach was uti-

lized, specifically adhering to Colaizzi's method for data analysis. This approach encompassed multiple stages: familiarizing oneself with the data, extracting key statements, formulating interpretations, grouping into themes, creating a comprehensive description, identifying the essential structure, and confirming the results. The

aim was to reveal the core of participants' collective experiences while staying true to their real stories.

2.5. Data Analysis—To enhance the robustness of the analysis, the research employed triangulation methods, which featured member checking, peer debriefing, and the utilization of field notes. Member checking included re-sending the analyzed data to participants for confirmation, guaranteeing that interpretations accurately represented their viewpoints. Peer review was also carried out with research mentors and TESDA instructors to confirm the thematic classifications and minimize possible researcher bias. Additionally, field notes and reflective journaling were kept during the interview process, recording non-verbal signals, emotional

nuances, and the researcher's personal observations. These notes were compared with the interview transcripts to improve the richness and context of the analysis. Through the use of triangulation, the research confirmed that the data were examined from various perspectives, thus improving the reliability and validity of the findings. This varied approach offered an extensive insight into the phenomenon, emphasizing the genuineness of the experiences shared by the participants. The integration of phenomenological thematic analysis and triangulation methods facilitated a deep and significant interpretation of the transition experience from private teaching to public service within TESDA.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter involves the live experiences of transitioning from private instructor to a TESDA instructor.

3.1. Live experiences of participants—Transitioning from private institutions to TESDA brought significant challenges for instructors, especially in adjusting to bureaucratic systems and protocols. Many participants felt overwhelmed by the extensive paperwork and documentation required, which differed greatly from the informal systems they were used to. Adapting to TESDA's strict chain of command also proved difficult, as decisions had to pass through multiple levels of approval. Former private instructors noted that understanding government language, including memos and circulars, required time and guidance. The reduced instructional autonomy was another major concern, with participants feeling restricted by TESDA's rigid adherence to Training Regulations. Creative teaching methods they previously enjoyed were no longer applicable, which they felt diminished student engagement. Stan-

dardized assessments also limited their ability to evaluate students in diverse and personalized ways. These constraints made the teaching experience feel less flexible and more mechanical for some instructors. Despite these struggles, many found motivation in obtaining national certification, which validated their skills and boosted their confidence. The process of certification also sparked a desire for further professional growth and continuous learning. National certifications provided a sense of legitimacy to instructors who previously lacked formal qualifications despite years of experience in the private sector. It elevated their credibility in the classroom and helped improve relationships with students, who saw them as both competent and certified. As instructors became more familiar with TESDA protocols and expectations, they began to embrace their new roles with renewed purpose. Some acknowledged that while their

Fig. 1. Live experiences of participants

autonomy was reduced, the structured approach helped standardize teaching quality across institutions. Others found value in mastering the government’s system, realizing it added professionalism to their teaching career. The identity shift—from being independent private instructors to compliant government educators—was both challenging and enlightening. Over time, instructors developed strategies to balance compliance with creativity, seeking small ways to

personalize their teaching within the framework. They also appreciated the opportunity to participate in national programs and contribute to skills development in the country. Ultimately, the transition was a journey of adaptation, learning, and professional transformation. These lived experiences highlight the complexity of shifting educational roles within institutional contexts.

3.2. Challenges or difficulties encountered.—Figure 2. The participants faced multiple challenges in their transition from private to TESDA instruction, including adapting to the demanding bureaucratic and regulatory requirements unfamiliar in their previous roles. They

experienced reduced teaching flexibility due to strict adherence to competency-based curricula, which constrained their instructional creativity. Emotionally, many struggled with stress and self-doubt as they navigated the pressures of meeting institutional expectations. Socially, ad-

justing to the formal and hierarchical culture of a government institution posed difficulties in workplace integration and relationships. Additionally, they encountered challenges in academic and professional development, needing to undertake new training and certification programs while managing existing workloads. The transition from private instruction to TESDA presented five major challenges for instructors, including professional, instructional, personal, social, and academic/professional development themes. Professionally, instructors faced difficulties adapting to government bureaucracy, especially the overwhelming paperwork and delayed processes caused by rigid approval systems. Instructionally, many struggled with limited teaching flexibility, as TESDA's strict adherence to Training Regulations and CBLMs reduced opportunities for creativity and personalized instruction. The standardized assessment system also narrowed their ability to evaluate soft skills and holistic learner development. On a personal level, instructors experienced emotional stress and self-doubt, particularly due to

the loss of instructional autonomy and constant pressure to comply with performance standards. Socially, participants had to adjust to a formal and hierarchical institutional culture, which slowed communication and made it harder to seek support or raise concerns. They also faced difficulty integrating into existing staff circles, often feeling isolated or excluded from long-established workplace dynamics. The shift to TESDA's value-driven mission further required them to realign their professional goals, contrasting with their customer-oriented private school background. Academically, the move from knowledge-based to competency-based teaching demanded a complete rethinking of instructional approaches. Many found the CBLMs overwhelming and restrictive, especially without proper training in competency-based instruction. Overall, these five themes reflect a multifaceted and often challenging transition process that required instructors to adapt not only professionally but also emotionally and socially.

3.3. *Coping mechanism to deal with*—Figure 3 shows to cope with the challenges of transitioning to TESDA instruction, participants employed several effective strategies. They sought guidance and emotional support from experienced colleagues, which eased their adjustment to the new environment. Engaging in continuous professional development, such as enrolling in TESDA's Trainers Methodology programs, helped them gain the necessary skills and confidence. Reflective teaching practices allowed them to adapt while maintaining their personal teaching style. Effective time and stress management strategies, including structured planning and task prioritization, helped them handle increased workloads. New TESDA instructors employed a variety of coping mechanisms to manage their transition from private institu-

tions, with peer support and mentorship serving as a vital foundation. Consulting senior TESDA instructors allowed them to grasp essential procedures such as documentation and assessment, fostering confidence early in their public teaching careers. Informal peer networks, often formed through group chats or shared lunch breaks, became emotional and intellectual havens where frustrations were aired and practical strategies exchanged. Shadowing experienced trainers further reinforced their confidence, offering them a front-row seat to observe effective teaching and assessment practices. Alongside these peer-based strategies, continuous professional development served as a structured way for instructors to strengthen their competence. Enrolling in National Certification (NC) trainings allowed them to meet

Fig. 2. Challenges or difficulties encountered

eligibility requirements and solidify their standing as credible technical trainers. Training Methodology (TM I) courses deepened their understanding of learner-centered teaching approaches, helping to bridge the gap between traditional instruction and competency-based education. TESDA-sponsored seminars and workshops provided ongoing learning opportunities and helped instructors stay aligned with institutional goals. Together, these efforts ensured that instructors not only survived but began to thrive in the TESDA environment. The synergy between peer collaboration and formal training laid the groundwork for personal growth and professional identity development. To sustain their momentum and adapt to the demands of their roles, instructors also embraced reflective teaching, time management, and a values-based mindset. Maintaining journals or notes allowed them to track teaching outcomes, helping them adjust strategies over time based on what worked or failed. By observing student reactions and soliciting feedback, they were able to customize lesson delivery for better engagement and comprehension. Reviewing session guides and comparing outcomes further encouraged a data-driven approach to instructional refinement. These reflective practices were complemented by effective time and stress management techniques, such as creating structured schedules to

organize tasks and avoid being overwhelmed. Instructors also prioritized breaks and personal time to recharge physically and emotionally. Establishing clear boundaries between work and personal life protected them from burnout and preserved their well-being. Beyond these strategies, reframing their experience with a deeper sense of purpose helped them cope with institutional pressures. Aligning their personal values with TESDA's mission of national workforce development reinforced their dedication and gave their work greater meaning. Viewing challenges as meaningful contributions to student success, and drawing inspiration from learner achievements, gave them the emotional fuel to persevere. Through this holistic approach, instructors transformed obstacles into opportunities for growth and purpose-driven teaching. The study reveals that the transition from a private instructor to a TESDA instructor is filled with challenges, such as adapting to institutional hierarchy, navigating diverse student populations, and managing emotional strain. However, the instructors employed various coping mechanisms, including seeking peer support, engaging in professional development, and adapting to TESDA's competency-based teaching model. These strategies helped them overcome the challenges and build a more fulfilling teaching experience in their new roles.

4. Implications of the Study

4.1. Findings—The study revealed that transitioning from a private institution to TESDA presents a multifaceted experience marked by both professional growth and emotional strain. Instructors encountered significant challenges adapting to the structured environment, including rigid administrative processes and the implementation of the competency-based education (CBE) model. Many struggled with reduced instructional autonomy and

had difficulty aligning traditional teaching methods with TESDA's standardized requirements. The diversity of student backgrounds also posed challenges, requiring instructors to adjust their approaches to meet varied learning needs. These experiences often led to feelings of uncertainty, stress, and self-doubt, particularly during the early stages of the transition.

4.2. Implications—To cope with these challenges, instructors relied on informal peer

Fig. 3. Coping mechanism to deal with

support, self-directed learning, and gradual adaptation through trial and error. Some found strength in developing a renewed sense of purpose aligned with TESDA's mission of skill development and national service. The importance of mentorship, professional development, and emotional resilience emerged as critical supports for easing the transition. Institutions are encouraged to implement structured onboarding programs, provide mental health resources, and offer continuous training focused on CBE and classroom management. These measures can enhance instructors' confidence, improve instructional quality, and foster a more supportive and sustainable teaching environment within the TVET sector.

4.3. *Future Directions*—TESDA instructors who transitioned from private institutions employed various coping mechanisms to navigate the challenges of their new roles. One of the most prominent strategies was seeking support from fellow instructors who had undergone similar transitions. Peer support provided

emotional reassurance and practical advice on handling bureaucratic processes and classroom management. Many instructors also turned to self-directed learning, reviewing TESDA guidelines and training regulations to better align with competency-based education. Attending professional development workshops helped them gain confidence and adapt to the technical-vocational teaching model. Some relied on time management techniques to balance increased workloads and administrative responsibilities. Others found solace in reflective practices, such as journaling or informal debriefing with colleagues, which helped them process their experiences. A few participants emphasized the importance of maintaining work-life balance by setting boundaries and engaging in personal hobbies. Prayer and spiritual practices also served as emotional anchors for those facing intense stress and uncertainty. Overall, these coping mechanisms collectively contributed to their resilience and gradual adaptation within the TESDA environment.

5. References

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